

Predicting Time-To-Failure Using Finite Element Analysis

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Abstract

RADC pioneered the application of finite element analysis (FEA) as a method to assess the reliability of surface mounted assemblies (SMA). As an increasing number of newly developed systems began to utilize SMA technology, it became apparent that a technique was needed to assess the reliability of design, as early as possible. FEA is a technique that determines the thermal and mechanical response of a device or system to outside environments. FEAs were performed on three different surface mounted designs; the leadless chip carrier, gull-wing chip carrier and compliant S-lead leadless chip carrier. The output of the FEA was inputted into the Coffin-Manson model and the number of thermal cycles to failure estimated. The results indicated that the gull-wing and S-lead chip carriers would be reliable when placed in this temperature environment but, the leadless chip carriers would have reliability problems after a short period of time.

Introduction

Many of the connections in advanced electronic packaging are made of either eutectic tin/lead solder or copper. When these materials are exposed to thermal cycling environments such as experienced by military aircraft, failure will occur after a period of time. Connections have particular importance because as advanced packaging designs become smaller and denser, these connections provide a mechanical support as well as a path for electrical signals. The integrity of these connections has become very critical to the reliability of certain technologies. An example of such a technology is Surface Mount Technology (SMT).

In order to evaluate the reliability of SMT, a FEA can be used. FEA is a computer simulation technique which predicts the thermal and mechanical response of structures exposed to various environmental conditions. Over the past several years, RADC has pioneered FEA to evaluate the reliability of new unproven technologies such as Very High Speed Integrated Circuits (VHSIC), Wafer Scale Integration (WSI), Gallium Arsenide (GaAs), Monolithic Microwave Integrated Circuits (MMIC), and Surface Mount Technology (SMT) (Ref. 1). These analyses investigated the response of these designs when exposed to steady state environmental conditions. To assess the reliability, a comparison was made between the stresses in the materials and the corresponding material strengths. This factor of safety procedure, strength in excess of stress, could not be used to assess the reliability in materials that fail due to thermal fatigue. Although traditional practices design for stresses below the yield strength, microelectronic designs typically exceed this strength value and plastic deformation occurs. This deformation leads to thermal fatigue. Thermal fatigue takes place when ductile materials are exposed to cyclic temperature changes. Since fatigue is a reliability concern, the ability to analyze its impact is important. This can be done by inputting the results of FEA into a proven relation known as the Coffin-Manson Model.

Surface Mount Technology

Surface Mounted Devices (SMDs) are mounted directly onto a board and soldered to its surface. This process differs from thru-hole mounting where the device lead is

inserted through a plated hole in the board and soldered into place. Some SMDs have leads while others are considered "leadless" when the edge of the package is attached directly to the board by solder. The location where the solder connects either the lead or the package to the board is considered the solder connection. When SMDs are exposed to thermal cycling environments, the package and the board materials expand at different rates and cause strain to occur in the solder connections. The eventual cracking of the solder connection is the major failure mode for SMT. The main design parameters which affect the integrity of these solder connections include the lead design, package size, board material and the ability to remove heat.

The main failure mechanisms for the solder connection failure mode are thermal fatigue and creep. Thermal fatigue is defined as failure under the repetitive application of thermal stress. Creep can be defined as the slow and progressive deformation of a material with time under a constant stress. These phenomenon combined accelerate the failure of the solder.

Finite Element Analysis

FEA was performed in order to determine the stresses induced in the solder connections. Three different surface mounted designs were analyzed: the leadless chip carrier (LCC); the S-lead chip carrier; and the gull-wing chip carrier. These three designs are displayed in Figure 1. The LCC and the S-lead packages evaluated had 32 interconnects and the gull-wing package had 172 interconnects.

FIGURE 1: SURFACE MOUNT DESIGNS

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For each lead design, two models were created. The first model represented the package mounted onto a board and the second represented a single lead. The package/board model was thermally cycled and the results inputted into the lead model in order to obtain a detailed stress distribution in the solder. Geometrical models, referred to as Finite Element Models (FEMs), of the SMDs mounted onto a board are displayed in Figures 2, 3 and 4. Due to symmetry, only one-quarter of the geometry was actually modeled. The corresponding lead FEMs are shown in Figures 5, 6, and 7. The output stress values from the lead FEA were used to calculate the elastic and plastic strain for each temperature cycle. The strain values were added together to give the solder's strain range.

In order to perform a FEA, a data file containing the FEM, material properties, input conditions, and boundary conditions was generated. These package/board FEMs were thermally cycled from a stress free temperature to the maximum temperature (high temperature cycle) and a stress free temperature to the minimum temperature (low temperature cycle). The output was transferred to the lead FEM and the output stress values in the solder material were obtained. The stress values from each cycle were transferred to strain values and the strain values for the high and low temperature cycles were combined. This final strain value represented the strain from one entire thermal cycle which started at the minimum temperature, went to the maximum temperature and then returned to the minimum temperature.

FIGURE 2: LEADLESS SYSTEM FEM

FIGURE 5: LEADLESS CONNECTION FEM

FIGURE 3: S-LEAD SYSTEM FEM

FIGURE 6: S-LEAD CONNECTION FEM

FIGURE 4: GULL-WING SYSTEM FEM

FIGURE 7: GULL-WING CONNECTION FEM

This analysis simulated elastic strain. The stress results from the majority of the analyses showed that the stress values exceeded the yield strength and, therefore, plastic strain also occurred. An approximation for the plastic strain had to be made. The approach taken put boundaries on the amount of plastic strain and assumed that the actual value was in between these two values. The lower plastic strain limit used the formula for elastic strain to calculate the plastic strain (strain = stress/modulus of elasticity). The upper limit assumed that the plastic strain was twice the value of the calculated elastic strain (i.e. twice the plastic strain used in the lower limit). Once these plastic strain values were estimated, the elastic and plastic strain for the high and low temperature cycles were combined to give the solder's strain range.

Coffin-Manson Model

The Coffin-Manson Model (Ref. 3) is an equation which relates a ductile material's strain to the number of cycles to failures. This equation is listed below along with the material parameters for both eutectic tin/lead solder and copper. The Coffin-Manson is used to generate a logarithmic graph. The curve generated for the solder is displayed in Figure 8. This curve allows the engineer performing the analysis to take the total strain range ($\Delta\epsilon$) obtained from the FEA and estimate the number of cycles to failure (N_f) for that material. The Coffin-Manson model has been in existence for many decades and has verified accuracy (Ref. 2).

$$\frac{\Delta \epsilon}{2} = \underbrace{\frac{\sigma_f}{E} (2N_f)^b}_{\text{ELASTIC STRAIN}} + \underbrace{\epsilon_f (2N_f)^c}_{\text{PLASTIC STRAIN}}$$

PARAMETER	COPPER	SOLDER
σ_f	50,050 psi	7,350 psi
ϵ_f	.3	.325
E	16×10^4 psi	1.09×10^4 psi
b	-.05	-.05
c	-.6	-.5

σ_f : FATIGUE STRENGTH COEFFICIENT
 ϵ_f : FATIGUE DUCTILITY COEFFICIENT
E : MODULUS OF ELASTICITY
b : FATIGUE STRENGTH EXPONENT
c : FATIGUE DUCTILITY EXPONENT

(1)

FIGURE 8: COFFIN-MANSON CURVE FOR SOLDER

Results

Several FEAs were performed and the resulting stress values used to estimate the strain. These stress and strain values are displayed in Table 1. The total strain range was then used to calculate the number of thermal cycles to failure. These values are listed in Table 2. An evaluation of these results indicate that, in this temperature environment, the leadless chip carriers will have a high number of solder connection failures in a relatively short period of time and the S-lead and gull-wing chip carriers will survive a significant number of temperature cycles before the solder connections begin to fail. Subsequent thermal cycling tests showed that the leadless chip carriers were not able to survive the accelerated thermal cycling tests but, the leaded design packages did.

TABLE 1: FEA OUTPUT VALUES

	HIGH TEMPERATURE CYCLE	LOW TEMPERATURE CYCLE
S-LEAD		
MAXIMUM LINEAR STRESS	6,000 psi	3,800 psi
PLASTIC STRESS	2,800 psi	700 psi
ELASTIC STRAIN	.0029 in/in	.0029 in/in
PLASTIC STRAIN	.0028 to .0052 in/in	.0008 to .0012 in/in
LEADLESS		
MAXIMUM LINEAR STRESS	23,400 psi	7,800 psi
PLASTIC STRESS	20,200 psi	4,400 psi
ELASTIC STRAIN	.0029 in/in	.0029 in/in
PLASTIC STRAIN	.0186 to .0370 in/in	.0041 to .0082 in/in
GULL-WING		
MAXIMUM LINEAR STRESS	2,700 psi	4,250 psi
PLASTIC STRESS	—	1,050 psi
ELASTIC STRAIN	.0025 in/in	.0029 in/in
PLASTIC STRAIN	—	.0010 to .0020 in/in

TABLE 2: ESTIMATED CYCLES TO FAILURE

	TOTAL STRAIN RANGE	NUMBER OF CYCLES TO FAILURE
S-LEAD	.0080 to .0122 in/in	11,500 to 60,000 cycles
LEADLESS	.0284 to .0510 in/in	120 to 260 cycles
GULL-WING	.0084 to .0074 in/in	400,000 to 2,000,000 cycles

Conclusions

As a result of this study, conclusions were made pertaining to the finite element modeling and to the technique used to assess the reliability. In regards to the modeling, a comparison of the FEA results for the three different package/board/lead models showed only a slight variation in package and board defections for the three models. This occurrence implies that the lead type has little effect on the package and board defections. Consequently, a single package FEM and a single board FEM could be generated and used for the analysis of many different lead types. In addition, the defections across the width of the leads (25 mils) in the package/board/lead model were essentially constant. These results indicate that since the inputs were constant along the third dimension, the leads could have been modeled in only two dimensions.

The technique documented here is just the first step in the development of a reliability assessment technique. The validity of performing a purely linear, elastic analysis and using the results to estimate the amount of plastic strain should be verified. A question arises as to the ability to predict the response of the material once it goes beyond the linear range. Since the results of this analysis went well into the plastic region, then a non-linear, elastic and plastic analysis should be considered. This area deserves further consideration.

• References

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Biography

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Gretchen Bivens received her B.S. in Mechanical Engineering in 1985 from SUNY at Buffalo and is currently pursuing an M.S. in Electrical Engineering from Syracuse University. She works as an Electronics Engineer for RADC's Systems Reliability and Engineering Division. Since 1985, she has worked in the areas of Finite Element Analysis and Surface Mount Technology and has written a number of technical reports on these topics. In 1988, she was awarded an Air Force Systems Command Scientific Achievement Award for her work on these subjects.